

Workshop on Engaging with the European Health Data Space: The Paediatric Perspective

February 19th - 20th 2024
Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Fonteyn Room, AMC

Background

[conect4children \(c4c\)](#) is an IMI2 initiative that was established to overcome the many barriers to the planning and delivery of effective and efficient paediatric clinical trials. The project stemmed from the fundamental recognition that there are not enough medicines designed specifically for the paediatric population, and that safety and efficacy data is correspondingly scarce. One route to better, faster, more streamlined clinical trials in paediatric diseases is an enhanced ability for data collected in disparate systems to be able to 'speak' with other data. Several resources have been developed over the course of c4c project to promote the standardization and harmonization of paediatric clinical trial data.

c4c hosted a workshop in Rome in May 2022 to bring together representatives from health and research related organizations, initiatives and projects working on different aspects of data harmonization, standardization and interoperability. The Global Paediatric Data Forum (GLOPAD) was formed as a result of this workshop.

c4c is challenged with finding ways to engage with the European Health Data Space. The GLOPAD will push the paediatric agenda, but it is not clear how to engage or whether it would ever be possible to submit data from c4c studies. The main purpose of this workshop is to explore increased alignment with the European Health Data Space and policy making in a European context.

Workshop Aims and Objectives

Explore how to increase alignment of c4c with the European Health Data Space and policy making in a European context.

Main aims

- To gain a better understanding of the European Health Data Space, upcoming European policy and legislation relating to health data.
- To present the case for paediatric information being included within the next version of the European Electronic Health Record eXchange Format.

- To undertake horizon scanning for new developments relating to paediatric data in clinical trials (e.g., AI, innovative trial design).
- To provide opportunities for networking, information sharing, mutual learning and collaboration opportunities between attendees.

Intended outcomes/outputs of the workshop

- A better understanding of the European Health Data Space.
- An action plan for how c4c and GLOPAD members can better engage with the European Health Data Space.
- A horizon scanning report on latest developments relating to paediatric clinical trials.
- Development or ideas for roadmap/action plan for capturing, aligning and making accessible paediatric data in line with the European Health Data Space.
- Outline of a white paper to convey the importance of this roadmap to key decision-making stakeholders.

Overview

The workshop had 49 attendees in total with overall participation evenly split between in person and online participants (see Annex 1). Online participants joined via Zoom. In person attendees were split into three different breakout groups and captured their ideas on flip charts (see Annex 2). Online participants engaged in breakout group activities using a Miro board (see Annex 3).

Day 1

Introduction to the workshop

Mark Turner gave an overview of [conect4children \(c4c\)](#), specifically the work that has been carried out under WP5 around the harmonization and standardization of paediatric clinical trial data. He also presented the [conect4children Stichting \(c4c-s\)](#), the new legal entity that will continue the work of c4c.

Becca Leary, Vicki Hedley, Ronald Cornet and Dipak Kalra provided information about the background to the workshop and Vicki Hedley gave an overview of the workshop aims and objectives.

Introduction to the European Health Data Space (EHDS)

Giulia Ancillotti Policy & Programme Officer at the European Commission presented the European vision for the [EHDS](#) and the European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format (EEHRxF).

The 2020 European Data Strategy announced the EC's plans for European Data Spaces, including the EHDS. The EHDS is organized around two key pillars – primary and secondary use of health data.

The EHDS will strengthen peoples' rights to access and control their own electronic health data across EU Member States through cross-border interoperability, specifically via the European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format (EEHRxF). The EEHRxF is a set of technical specifications, targeted at ensuring the interoperability of electronic health record systems used in the EU which will support the exchange of both structured and unstructured data.

The EHDS will connect all Member States to [MyHealth@EU](#) by 2025 and expand access from patient summaries and ePrescriptions / eDispensations to lab results, medical images, hospital discharge reports and others.

The secondary use of health data will support reuse of data to promote more research, better treatments, improved patient care and better policy making. Secondary use of data will happen through a second platform, [HealthData@EU](#). Through this platform, any researcher will be able to find out what data exists to perform their research. Through a health data access application, a permit will be issued to ensure data quality and privacy. Data processing will take place in a secure environment.

Negotiations are ongoing with the goal to reach a tentative agreement on the proposed regulation in Spring 2024. If the regulation is adopted, the EC will specify the technical details by implementing Acts. After the regulation has entered into force, it will apply to all Member States.

Roger Lim, Policy Coordinator at the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare & Sport presented the Dutch perspective on the EHDS. New Dutch legislation, the [Wegiz](#) (the Electronic Exchange of Health Data Act), was approved in parliament last year. The Wegiz regulates that data is exchanged electronically - it creates technical requirements around how data exchange takes place and imposes requirements for access to individual health data. A 3rd party certification scheme has also been implemented for EHR systems. The Wegiz does not regulate which type of data is digitally made available or the legal basis for exchanging data, these will be addressed in governmental decrees. Unlike the EHDS, the Wegiz does not focus on use of secondary data.

The Dutch national contact point for eHealth went live in February 2022 with a minimal use case of receiving patient summaries from other countries. This was followed by a use case to send patient summaries abroad. Work is ongoing to make the national contact points ready for ePrescriptions.

The strategy for how to deal with secondary use of data was sent to Parliament in April 2023. The national vision includes some requirements from the EHDS, including setting up a data access body in the Netherlands.

Primary use of health data in the EHDS

The next section focused on gaining a better understanding of the EHDS and the primary use of health data.

Henrique Martins, Coordinator of XpanDH presented [XpanDH](#) (Expanding Digital Health through a pan-European EHRxF-based Ecosystem)

XpanDH supports efforts for adoption of the EEHRxF. XpanDH intends to build up the EEHRxF through a collaborative process within the eHealth community. Early adopters' organizations will be grouped under selected adoption domains, or X-Bubbles. An X-Bubble is a list of organizations that will collaborate within the project to jointly adopt and demonstrate use of digital solutions (including interoperability) for an adoption domain.

A proposed next step from this workshop would be a proposal to create a paediatric X-Bubble.

Theodoros Kyprianou, Medical Expert at Xt-EHR presented on the roles and opportunities presented by the [Xt-EHR](#) for the paediatric community and paediatric research. The goal is to combine all the necessary elements to achieve an effective healthcare workflow in primary and secondary care by:

- The adoption of common requirements and specifications on interoperability and health information.
- Evaluating telemedicine, mobile health and other health software in the context of the EEHRxF and the EDHS regulation proposal.
- Evaluating common EHR requirements for electronic identification for health professionals and patients and the necessary metadata layer needed.
- Evaluating the sustainability of cross-border telemedicine services, including telemonitoring.
- Preparing a guideline and interoperability requirements for mobile wellness applications and provide a respective conformity assessment and/or labelling scheme.
- Providing a conformity assessment scheme for the certification of EHRs under the EHDS regulation.

Catherine Chronaki, Scientific Coordinator of xSHARE presented on [xSHARE](#) and how it will operate to extend the EHDS with new use cases and multi-stakeholder collaborations. A sustainable entity, the EEHRxF Standards and Policy Hub, will be created as a result of this work. The Hub currently includes six standards organizations and engages industry and the Global Digital Health Partnership. The xSHARE vision is for everyone to be able to share their health data in the EEHRxF with the click of a button.

xSHARE aims to connect three traditional pillars: direct healthcare, public health and clinical research. Of interest to this group, is a project work package co- led by CDISC and I~HD, the outcome of which will be an extension to the IPS to make it useful for research (including clinical trials). This could have a specific

extension that relates to children. CDISC have been working to map the IPS to specific elements in clinical trials. This is a work in progress and a draft deliverable will be ready in May 2024.

The EEHRxF format, technical specifications, tools and testing and adoption experience will form an X-Bundle under a specific use case adoption exercise. Decision makers, caregivers, informaticians will be engaged to ensure quality. The process will be flexible enough to accommodate changes.

Possible next steps:

- c4c and the GLOPAD collaborate with xShare and its Hub to develop a business use case and participate in the open call of xShare with a bridge proposal IPS-R for children.
- Experts can engage with xShare and the Hub to be xShare ambassadors or liaisons and engage with the annual work plan of the Hub. Contribute material to the Hub for the X-Bundles to accelerate adoption. Explore revenue sharing models for materials to be jointly developed and maintained. Validate results, harmonize across use cases. Share business use cases.
- Help share the vision for an xShare industry label: liberating health data.

Primary Use Panel Discussion

Following the presentations, Dipak Kalra led a panel discussion to explore how the EHDS could deliver for children at a primary level, to identify any gaps that need to be closed and to ensure the rights of children and their proxies are considered in cross-border care.

Children with a specific developmental pathway have different responses to medicines which are themselves dependent on their development. The interaction of the child themselves, potentially the family, the conditions they are living with, and their developmental stage all need to be integrated in the clinicians' mind at the time of the encounter. It may also be important to carry forward information about life-long conditions that occur from birth and to take into account normal lab ranges changing as the child grows. Children and young people themselves need to be involved in discussion about policy issues.

With the increasing prevalence of sequencing for children it may be necessary to plan ahead to include genetic and genomic data. The Xt-EHR is based on the Snomed vocabulary which includes rare diseases. It is important to not confuse the extended patient record with the exchangeable electronic health care summary. Part of the Xt-EHR project is a special activity to see how the reports of DNA sequencing and omics in general will be incorporated into the patient record and what structured format should be stored there.

There is a need for long-term safety data in paediatrics as 60% of indications are off label. Children are a major demographic in rare diseases and the distances rare disease patients need to travel limits enrolment into studies.

The useability of a standard is important and road testing it for both care and research was identified as a **hot topic**.

There is a need for EHR systems to be smarter to automatically maintain the patient summary and prompt or help clinicians when typing clinical notes to improve the quality of their entry and the summary (i.e., to improve the quality of the source data).

There needs to be evidence of economic growth and a business case that will convince post-COVID governments to invest. EHR vendors will not invest unless they think there is a market and a budget. The benefit from decisions being made now will only be seen in the future so the best business case is to consider what happens if we do nothing at all. The EC is negotiating with member states and holding technical and political discussions with co-legislators to advance the arguments that resulted from the impact assessment and stakeholder consultations conducted in 2021. Some member states are more advanced than others and will be more likely to be proactive. The EC is adopting pilots so member states can hit the ground running when the legislation is approved.

Secondary use of health data in the EHDS

The afternoon session started with a series of presentations to help understand the EHDS and the use of secondary use of health data from different perspectives:

- Daniel Morales, Data Analytics and Methods Task Force, EMA: [European Medicines Agency \(EMA\)](#) and [DARWIN EU](#) (The Data Analysis and Real World Interrogation Network).
 - Increasing acceptance of RWE in regulatory decision making.
 - RWE can be used at all stages for the drug development cycle.
- Marta Pineda Moncusi, University of Oxford: [EHDEN](#) (European Health Data and Evidence Network)
 - Multiple challenges to using real world data, including a range of languages and coding systems, different data structure, different policy restrictions.
 - EHDEN's solution is the use of a common data model - OMOP-CDM to create a European federated network to harmonize data.
- Ronald Cornet, Amsterdam UMC: European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases ([EJP RD](#)) and the European Reference Networks ([ERNs](#)).
 - Need a joint effort on FAIR data.
 - Work needs to be integrated across projects (RD / paediatrics / registries) with aligned standards, terminologies and data models.
- Sinead Nally, Novartis and co-lead of the c4c WP5 data harmonization and standardization tasks: Industry perspective.
 - EHDS *could* provide a legal basis for processing health data under GDPR.
- Gulcin Gumus and Jelena Malinina, European Organisation for Rare Diseases ([EURORDIS](#)): Patients' views on data protection and data sharing.
 - Almost 100% of rare disease patients surveyed want to share their research data.

- o EHDS offers a good opportunity for RD patients.
 - o Important to ensure ethical data re-use and work together in a private public partnership.
- Ed Neilan, [NORD](#) (National Organization for Rare Disorders) and Ramona Walls, [C-Path](#) (Critical Path Institute): US perspective and data sharing within the USA, North America and between the US and EU.
 - o Challenging to share data within the US. Hospitals within the same area are owned by different corporations and use different medical records with no legal access.
 - o Hospitals can charge patients for requesting their medical records. Patients are not protected from being unable to get life insurance or disability insurance or long-term care as a result of a genetic test.
 - o Data is in lots of different places depending on whether it is an academic or industry study. The challenge is not just in accessing data but in harmonizing it due to so many different healthcare systems. COVID showed it's possible to integrate data in an emergency.
 - o People in 'North America' don't think of it as a place. Canada has tighter regulations around data than the US and Mexico less.
 - o EU regulations are a little stricter than US regulations. The GDPR makes it more complicated to get data into the US, unless data is anonymized. NORD have servers in Canada and C-PATH have servers in Amsterdam to manage data sharing restrictions. There are a lot of interactions that are helping such as EJP RD and rare disease partnership.
 - o The potential to access longitudinal data within the EHDS will be helpful although the challenge will be around what standards will be used. The US would probably not contribute data but would hopefully be on an equal footing to access data.
 - o If you want a lot of good quality data collected during routine healthcare, additional resources are needed to ensure good data quality and to incentivize good data collection. There is the issue of consent with the EHDS for research use of data.
 - o The EHDS needs to address the same data sharing challenges that everyone else. Infrastructure, standards and adoption need to be addressed from the outset.

Secondary Use Panel Discussion

After the presentations, Dipak Kalra led a second panel discussion to explore how the EHDS could deliver for children at a secondary use level.

There are many different standards that could potentially be used so it may be useful to have a 'standards book' for the EHDS. Standards should be self-describing and adhere to open API specifications. Standards must be maintained in the long-term and there are several examples of mappings between existing systems. Not all standards are well maintained, and poorly maintained standards can be dropped. Terminologies and information models need to be aligned so that they work well together, without excessive duplication, ambiguity or gaps.

What can be done to ensure the EHDS will be available and useful for research purposes, particularly in children?

Primary use data is defined as data that is captured for the purpose of delivering healthcare. Secondary use data is for a purpose other than what it was originally collected for. However clinical trial data falls in the middle and this may be a problem. It would be helpful to have clarity around whether clinical trial data is classed as primary use data within the EHDS – primary use data is tightly coupled to the exchange format so is almost certainly not fit for purpose for clinical trial data. Different types of data, including clinical trial data fall within different regulations.

Limitations around data sharing are driven by adult concerns, not paediatric concerns. Data sharing is the only thing that will help a child with a rare disease, so they (and their families) have no problem with sharing data. There is a concern that adult regulations will limit paediatric knowledge discovery and innovation.

Industry is in favour of having stricter data standards or better data definitions. When using registry data, industry needs to make sure the data are in line with what regulators expect at submission. However, in paediatrics and rare disease, there may not be alternative data sets. It would be useful to have more boundaries around definitions in the EHDS to make data useable for regulatory purposes.

Currently, the regulations say a data holder may (optionally) add a data quality label to data sets they make available via the EHDS. Hopefully it will soon become mandatory. For many data holders, it is already an obligation. When data is generated or registered using public money, there is a mandatory requirement to have that label.

Can the distinction between care and research disappear? This distinction is already almost invisible for rare diseases.

NORD is working with a network of rare disease centres of excellence across the US. One goal is to capture high quality data on as many of those patient encounters as possible. A lot of the data coming in from small patient organizations is often not useful due to quality issues. Until there is consistency between the way data are collected for health care the way data are collected for research or clinical trials, we will never realize the dream of secondary use of healthcare data.

The industry representatives were asked if industry would consider sponsoring the cost of people from healthcare going to data quality workshops to make RWD better. This would not be taken up by a single company, but the Moonshot Initiative is looking into training curricula.

The data that is collected and used for clinical decision making and reimbursement can be of poor quality but should be of the same standard. If the accreditation organization bodies could be persuaded

to implement data standards, this could go a long way towards a single standard of quality data for every type of decision making.

The cost of medicines and how medicines are paid for varies by country. If data were public, small companies would be able to access it and the costs may be reduced.

If industry can benefit from better RWD, and it lowers the cost of the trial, is there a way in which the health sector can then benefit from the cost of drugs being lowered? Generating the data in clinical studies is not without cost so this is unlikely.

The issue of data quality may be a derived problem with underlying issues of trust. If we aspire to collect a large amount of data, we may end up with almost nothing because finite data entry effort will be distributed across a wide landscape of data elements. There needs to be caution about what is feasible and acknowledge what is being collected and why and periodically revise what is still relevant. When people don't trust the quality of other people's data, they start from scratch.

A work package in xSHARE is looking into adding a modest extension to the IPS that optimizes its usefulness for clinical research without overloading it. It doesn't include a paediatric perspective; however, this work has already been done with the development of the CDISC Pediatrics User Guide and CDISC is a partner in xSHARE.

Several years ago, the European Joint Action for rare diseases, RD-ACTION, initiated collaborations with several eHealth projects. It was apparent that the ePatient Summary, as it was then known, was not suitable for rare diseases because the coding nomenclature it employed was not sufficiently sensitive to capture exact diagnoses. Once the RD-ACTION eHealth Taskforce had identified this important gap, via a series of calls and meetings, Orphanet advanced a piece of work to incorporate the OrphaCode into the IPS. This is important to note, as it constitutes a precedent for amending the IPS to better serve the needs of particular (and particularly vulnerable) communities in cross-border care. (<https://www.ehealth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D5.6-Refine-PS-functional-specifications-to-account-for-eHN-Guidelines-and-rare-diseases.pdf>)

The minimal dataset in the IPS is an artifact that suffers from quality issues within the source EHR systems that will populate summaries. There is a need to talk about good quality data, metadata, terminologies, information models and data sets. This minimal dataset mixes the raw data and the query about the record. Recommendation to take the concept of this minimal data set to existing standards and then say how in a minimally invasive way, the model can be implemented in a standard. There is also the Vulcan project which is looking at bridge building.

Clinicians are overburdened with administrative tasks and this needs to be addressed by compensation to clinicians and hospitals if the quality of the data entered into EHRs is to improve. A labelling system

that allows for the assessment of data quality coming from another hospital would be useful, or an algorithm that sense-checks what has been entered.

The first day ended with a wrap up of what had been learned.

Slides and recordings of the presentations are available on request from unew_imi2team@ncl.ac.uk.

Day 2

Consolidation and action planning

The second day of the workshop opened with a presentation from John Owen, Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium ([CDISC](#)). In February 2023, CDISC published the [Pediatrics User Guide](#) in collaboration with c4c. John presented an overview of the data items to help frame the following breakout session.

Breakout session

The in-person attendees were split into three groups with a fourth online breakout group. The groups in the room used flip charts to capture their ideas and the online group used a Miro board. Participants were asked to explore how to make International Patient Summary (IPS) and European Health Data Space more suitable for children and paediatric clinical research. The topic was broken down into the following sub-topics to aid discussion:

- Prospective vs retrospective data/data dictionaries/metadata/FAIR
- Transition from childhood to adulthood
- Long-term follow-up post-clinical trial
- Hot topics from first day

A representative from each group reported back to the larger group at the end of the breakout session. The flip charts and Miro Boards are in Annex 2 and 3 below.

Liesbeth Siderius, [European Academy of Paediatrics](#), presented on the digitization of primary healthcare and gave the perspective of paediatricians and patient representatives. This led into the second breakout session looking at the relationship between clinical research and clinical care.

The second breakout session was structured in the same way as the first, with groups in the room and a group online. A representative fed back to the wider group at the end of the session. The flip charts and Miro Boards are in Annex 2 and 3 below.

Becca Leary, Dipak Kalra and Ronald Cornet summarized learnings from the workshop and the action plan detailed below was agreed for capturing, aligning and making accessible paediatric data in line with the EHDS.

Slides and recordings of the presentations are available on request from
unew_imi2team@ncl.ac.uk.

Workshop Actions

- A white paper. Becca Leary will check with Anando Sen on how much overlap there will be with the Pediatrics User Guide (PUG) paper.
- Letter to the Archives of Disease in Childhood summarizing paediatric-specific concepts to raise awareness of data standards among health care professionals.
- Possible collaboration with European Academy of Paediatrics.
- Mapping between IPS and the PUG data items. This can be completed within the remaining c4c project timeframe. Dipak Kalra will follow up with Catherine Chronaki to enable this to happen.
- Promotion and dissemination.
- Collecting knowledge about resources, standards etc. through GLOPAD.
- EJP RD / ERDERA will deal with some of the rare disease and registry tasks, but we need colleagues like Ronald Cornet and Annalisa Landi to keep pushing the paediatric agenda.
- Dipak Kalra will follow up with Henrique Martins on his idea for a paediatric X-Bubble.
- Simon Woodworth is working on a registry for cerebral palsy, and they plan in principle to standardize as much as possible. Paper opportunity for a narrative of how the principles c4c have worked on either help or hinder building a registry.
- Message for people living with rare conditions and their families: There will be standards that underpin the EHDS. Now is the time to lobby on the content of those standards so they reflect the needs of children and young people with rare conditions. Link to white paper.

Updated Actions Following Consolidation

White paper

- The Newcastle University team will start drafting the white paper based on the information in the meeting report. Stakeholders and workshop attendees who have expressed an interest in being involved in the white paper will be invited to contribute.
- The Newcastle University team will engage with c4c patient/YPAG experts for their input on the paper.

Collaboration with xSHARE

- Becca Leary will look into setting up an MoU between c4c and xSHARE.
- Dipak Kalra will propose delaying the CDISC xSHARE deliverable to allow time for concepts from the PUG to be mapped to the IPS_R.

Letter to the Archives of Disease in Childhood

- The Newcastle University team will lead on finalizing the letter with Mark Turner.

Appendix 1: Attendees

Attending workshop in person	
Cintia Spira	Radboud University Medical Center
Daniel Morales	EMA
Dipak Kalra	I~HD
Duccio Bonifazi	Benzi Foundation
Edward Neilan	NORD
Gulcin Gumus	EURORDIS
Heidrun Hildebrand	Bayer
Jelena Malinina	EURORDIS
Jessie Trueman	Newcastle University
Joanne Lee	Newcastle University
John Owen	CDISC
Levi Hoste	Ghent University
Liesbeth Siderius	European Academy of Paediatrics
Mark Turner	University of Liverpool / c4c-s
Michael Davis Tira	Penta
Ramona Walls	C-Path
Rebecca Leary	Newcastle University
Ricardo Fernandes	AIDFM / c4c-s
Roger Lim	European Health Data Space
Ronald Cornet	Amsterdam UMC
Salma Malik	ECRIN
Simon Woodworth	University College Cork
Theodoros Kyprianou	Xt-EHR
Thomas Luethy	Bayer
Vicki Hedley	Newcastle University
Attending workshop virtually	
Anando Sen	Newcastle University
Annalisa Landi	Benzi Foundation
Avril Palmeri	Newcastle University
Caterina Deruvo	CVBF
Catherine Chronaki	xSHARE
Christian Ohmann	Research Data Alliance
Claudia Pansieri	CVBF
Daniele Giachello	CVBF
Eva Degraeuwe	Ghent University
Flogert Dollani	CVBF
Francesca Rocchi	OPBG
Giorgio Reggiardo	CVBF
Giulia Ancillotti	European Commission
Henrique Martins	XpanDH
Johan Vande Walle	Ghent University
Kasey Baker	NORD

This project has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 777389.

The Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

Kristina an Haack	Sanofi
Marina Montanaro	CVBF
Marta Pineda Moncusi	University of Oxford
Melissa Walsh	University College Cork
Nunzia D'Ercole	Benzi Foundation
Sinéad Nally	Novartis
Steven Hirschfeld	Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences
Teresa Berkery	University College Cork

Annex 2: Flip Charts

Hot Topics from Day 1

Day 2: Breakout Session: Prospective vs Retrospective/Data Dictionaries/Metadata/FAIR

Some tools we use
Missing standardisation in
paediatrics

Capacity building needed.
Takes burden away from
clinician entering info

Role of AI?

- natural language processing

Ethics of AI need to ensure
paediatrics included
particularly Consent/Assent

When at table making sure
we say "have you thought about?"
but also give solutions

Age not independent

Age inclusive

Context of use dependent
inclusivity in context

What do we want to tell the world about the paediatric user group?

PUG an example of using already available standards

Political arguments
children not mini adults

Discrimination in research against children under guise of protecting them.

Inclusion in clinical care + research

Don't want to lose data when children reach 18

Public health protection of other populations

Which tables do we want
a seat at?

Carry out landscape
analysis

- Vulcan
- Joint action
- X share

capture
hierarchy

Who?

- CDISC
- patients

Make sure we get across paediatric
specific aspects.

Structured vs

Where are we ^{unstructured} now + where are we heading

Consider organisational process

- Data set comprehensive as possible
life long data record
- usability of standards
- can we arrange for PUG
data items reviewed by
children?

Encourage national disease registries
to be interoperable - collect the same data
so they can be analysed consistently

Examine how consent for health data access (IPs)
+ reuse for research should evolve through
the early years with increasing autonomy
The same for transparency

How do we help amplify the voice of children
and rare diseases in the EHDS?

Atomisation of rare + genetic data

Patients as
data carriers
→ contribution
with the ICF
(Patient Perspective)

Gather
Natural history
Data
(Pediatric prep)

against
items

...

QC WORKED
EXAMPLE IN
ANOTHER FUNDED
PROJECT

Transliterate

Day 2: Breakout Session: Clinical Research vs Clinical Care

① Relationship between Clinical research + Clinical Care

- Keep life simple for
Clinician + person receiving
Care
- Keep encounter as human as possible
- AI use to bridge gap between
coding structured + unstructured
data — not there yet
- Is there a larger role for
patient in giving data? e.g. entering
data at home
Process needed
- proactive approach to implementing
data standards

2. Implementing data standards
needs to be properly resourced
- like a trial in itself
- Are all encounters useful
for research or some encounters
more useful than others?
- No simple answer but
may have to make a choice
Diagnosis could be an example
- Are we collecting data
needlessly?
Don't know what you might
use data for
Make intelligent choices based
on past ^{+ statistics} e.g. AEs
 - Focus on certain diseases
e.g. Rare diseases

- ③. Needs to be a rational + purpose for what we are collecting
- Need to be able to explain the why.
 - language important i.e. in consent forms
 - Is there a use case in undiagnosed?
 - when a RD is suspected?
role of AI?
 - role of genetic testing?
 - Protocol for interpreting data?
 - Is there a need for a committee to review e.g. say it collecting too much.
Already exists?
Risk proportionate could be considered by a committee

④ Take home message
Efficient process needed
that limits burden on those
entering data.
• hypothesis driven research

Patients as data providers.

Both care + research.

Wearable / App derived data - validation??

Across indications
↪ Regulatory acceptance

Regulatory culture change

Particularly useful in paediatrics

RWD Data Sources

Some key messages

Cannot divorce care + research

Promote adoption of interoperability standards

Promote importance of data quality

Promote child-centred design into a predominantly adult-thinking e Health landscape

Promote the importance of public-private collaboration to address
advance research + accelerate it

- Data set comprehensive as possible
life long data record
- Usability of Standards
- can we arrange for PUG
data items reviewed by
children?

Engage the needs of children in standards development (via patient organisations)

Promote PUG within Clinical Trial Network

- C4C Hubs + study centres
- Pharma
- eCRF + EDC developers
- EUCROF

Public awareness of the value of

- clinical trial participation
- health data being reused for research

(Also to clinical sites?)

Annex 3: Miro Board

Day 2: Breakout Session: Prospective vs Retrospective/Data Dictionaries/Metadata/FAIR

Someone, somewhere, needs to really work on registries in the RD and paediatric space, to get all stakeholders round the table and find out what data needs to be collected, going forward, to be able to use that data as RWE. Academic long-term registries are important tools but need a renewed focus on quality, completeness, data dictionaries, etc. to unlock power.

Conversion to SDTM (CDISC) standard that Ramona mentioned - Could this be done at a larger scale? Potential Pooling .

Format conversion between repositories a challenge. Claudia noticed no uniformity in formats when researching repositories.

encourage paediatric community to deposit their trial data in one of the repositories deemed most relevant/appropriate for paediatrics - having some sort of c4c 'recommendation' would be good

Day 2: Breakout Session: Transition from childhood to adulthood

Transition from birth to childhood not just childhood to adulthood

Continuity of care

Childhood passports

Age specific information and assent forms

So we agree it's crucial - something the EHDS should facilitate

Important to keep both paediatric and adult data for patients

Consent - different ages in different countries

Not a complete record all in one place and who has access to those records - carers/patients

Day 2: Breakout Session: Long-term follow up post clinical trial

Particularly important for patients transitioning from children transitioning to adulthood and getting a new treatment. Need datasets covering both adults and children (e.g., paediatric and adult SMA registries that an't talk to each other)

Could PACS help? Rules in different countries may be different.

Day 2: Breakout Session: Hot topics from day 1

Day 2: Breakout Session: Relationship between clinical research and clinical care

Understanding the status quo better (and what is possible)!

Mapping the Level of Digitalization of both resources (eCRF and EHR)

Wearable technology? Access rights to data, devices work differently, different companies

Investigate how source data can be verified and 'transmitted' to an eCRF without the need for additional data entry

Continue sort of work we've done in WP5 on understanding the readiness of even the 'best' EHRs to serve as RWE

Victoria Hedley 🧐 2

Understanding level of digitalisation - starting point

Promoting good practices & sharing of success in breaking down barriers between care and research

Including with countries outside of EU

Processes, enablers around process

Could the recording of clinical care (e.g., clinical notes) be adjusted in a way that it can be used (seamlessly) for clinical research?

General standards or best practices for data collection in visits, whatever form they are in (ex: Telehealth)

Education sessions/webinars to discuss the importance of standardization in non-technical language

Greater patient advocate engagement

Incentivising clinicians etc to create better, more comprehensive and useful care data to be reuseable

Need instruments/processes to help sites understand the reasons for data collection e.g., how the data will be analysed and what we expect to gain from the analysis. Part of feasibility discussions.

clinical research alignment with clinical care to improve evidence generation for drug development (win/win)t

